

Report on existing Research & Innovation Strategies (DI.I)

Daniel Brandt & Sigrður Beck, University of Gothenburg; Kerry Kirwan & Harriet Hine, University of Warwick; Enric Vallduví & Eva Martín García, University Pompeu Fabra; Frédéric Vidal, Cergy Université; Tania Van Loon, Vrije Universiteit Brussel and Mrak-Jamnik, Staška & Simona Rataj, University of Ljubljana.

Corresponding author: sigrður.beck@gu.se

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Executive summary

This document constitutes the EUTOPIA-TRAIN deliverable 1.1 described in the TRAIN Grant Agreement as: *Report on existing research & innovation strategies*.

This report will support the six partner institutions in the ongoing definition of which perspectives and themes to include in the common research and innovation agenda of TRAIN. We highlight similar strategies and discuss how and if the SWOT analysis (a part of a separate EUTOPIA 2050 project funded under Erasmus+ programme, project number 612361) can further support a common approach to strengthening research capacity, impact and efficiency across the alliance.

The current individual R&I strategies of each EUTOPIA TRAIN partner show strong common features, on which a future common agenda can be built:

- They reflect the fundamentals of the Humboldtian Ideals and the Magna Charta Universtitatum within their respective research and innovation strategies.
- They all state that sustainable development is an important/crucial virtue for a contemporary university.
- They all underline the importance of bottom-up approaches for creating the best environments for free inquiry and scientific discovery.
- They show similar ambitions of transferring new knowledge into society to create positive impacts, be it innovations or positive social impact by contributing to policy development.
- They all lay out similar types of missions/goals/themes within their respective research and innovation strategies.

Differences are mostly related to the wording, framing and respective weights of these shared building blocks within the visions, overarching aims and policies of each university.

Introduction

One of the aims of TRAIN is to develop a common research and innovation agenda. This report is the first step in this development and is intended to be used as a support tool for the management of the TRAIN project and the other work packages within TRAIN.

The picture below illustrates how the work packages are interlinked. Work package 1 functions in an overarching way to ensure that results from the other WPs are captured, coordinated, and disseminated effectively. The deliverables in WP1 are therefore interlinked with deliverables from across the project and represent a combination of bottom-up and top-down approaches.

The intention of having a common research and innovation agenda is to jointly enable the promotion of excellence in research and innovation to a level that cannot be reached by any single institution. It is therefore important to gather the existing strategies and discuss similarities and differences. This was described in the Grant Agreement definition of the project objectives:

“One of the key aims of EUTOPIA is to foster the emergence of a challenge-driven, knowledge-creation community, capitalising on the potential of the six research driven universities to promote innovation and societal impact. The importance of equipping the European research and education communities with the tools and expertise required to address economic and societal challenges is widely acknowledged. The Horizon Europe programme emphasises the importance of challenge-led research and the adoption of coordinated approaches to the deployment of academic resources and capabilities to deliver positive change.

The complete academic environment – recognising the interconnectivity between the research, innovation and education agendas – is central to the design and delivery of this project. In response to these imperatives, the overall objective of WP1 is to develop an overarching Research and Innovation Agenda for the EUTOPIA alliance and to share learnings from this development with key stakeholders. This will underpin a common approach to strengthening research capacity, impact and efficiency across the alliance in the following areas:

- *Defining key research challenge themes aligned with economic and societal priorities*

- *Developing an alliance research strategy, assimilating the results from WP2, WP3 and WP4 to bring new insights on collaborative modalities for innovation, university-business collaboration, open science and human capital*
- *Defining alliance key research themes aligned with economic and societal challenges (sic)*
- *Establishing an integrated approach to sharing of research resources including infrastructures and facilities, where possible*
- *Embedding mechanisms for real-time information capture to support a cost-benefit analysis (CBA) to understand the impact of the actions undertaken on the building of the EUTOPIA R&I ecosystem*
- *Dissemination and communication of learnings and outputs.”¹*

¹ EUTOPIA TRAIN (Projekt Number 101017419) Grant Agreement p 9.

Research & innovation strategies at an institutional level

Today most higher education institutions adhere to research and innovation strategies as a part of their overarching visions at an institutional level. Also, the European University Association, EUA, launched a vision *Universities without walls* in February 2021, and in January 2022 the European Commission launched *The European Strategy for Universities*.² There is a high demand on universities to be more active in formulating strategies to find current and future solutions to the global challenges we are facing. European universities are seen as lighthouses of a European way of life where European values are embodied and therefore seen as essential parts in the green and digital transformation that needs to take place.

Sharing a common vision is not new for European universities. The Humboldtian model of higher education is a concept of academic education that emerged in the early 19th century. The core idea is a holistic combination of research and studies that integrates the arts and sciences with research to achieve both comprehensive general learning and cultural knowledge. In German the goal of this higher education was defined as *Bildung*, that translates into cultivation or cultural literacy.

*"To Humboldt and his contemporaries, Bildung had to do with the highest and most harmonious development of natural human abilities. His theoretical expositions on the concept of Bildung demonstrated a kind of duality in his thought. On the one hand, he described an educational process in which the unrestricted improvement of each person's personality was at the centre. Humboldt's Bildung was based on a subjective acquisition of knowledge that had its origins in and transformed the individual. On the other hand, an individual's development was always considered in relation to history and to the truly human. The realisation of that individual's inner potential took place in a dialectical movement between the self and the surrounding culture. In this dynamics, Humboldt imagined that that which is individual could approach that which is generally human."*³

This idea that university education should offer knowledge that transforms the individual, and at the same time consider this development in relation to history, is somewhat reflected in the *European Universities Initiative*.

"The aim of this initiative is to bring together a new generation of creative Europeans able to cooperate across languages, borders and disciplines to address societal challenges and skills shortages faced in Europe."

² The EUA document available at <https://education.ec.europa.eu/document/commission-communication-on-a-european-strategy-for-universities>, the EC communication at <https://education.ec.europa.eu/document/commission-communication-on-a-european-strategy-for-universities>.

³ Östling, Johan, *Humboldt and the Modern German University; An intellectual history*, Lund University Press, 2018, p 38.

“[...] The 41 European University alliances will test different models of the concept of European Universities and examine its potential to transform higher education.”⁴

At first glance, the aim of the *European Universities Initiative* might be perceived to conflict with the Humboldtian ideal. However, to strive for the Humboldtian ideal is a constant process that paradoxically will never truly be achieved. To aspire to the Humboldtian ideal, can be viewed as a constant process of transformation, so the idea for European Universities to examine its own potential to transform higher education lies within the nature of a Humboldtian university itself. Furthermore, as a university is not its walls, but the people inside. One would be hard-pressed to distinguish between the university as a structure and the individuals who reside within it. It is the responsibility of a university that subscribes to these ideals to continuously transform itself in order to transcend from merely being to be truly living.

These ideals are further emphasized in the *Magna Charta Universitatum*, which all of the EUTOPIA TRAIN partners have signed and pledged to adhere to. The charter, administrated by The Observatory was created and first signed 1988 on the 900th anniversary of the University of Bologna. It was updated to resonate with contemporary challenges and concerns in 2020, but it did not remove any of the original fundamental values to which universities had first signed up:

“The first principle was independence: research and teaching must be intellectually and morally independent of all political influence and economic interests. The second was that teaching and research should be inseparable, with students engaged in the search for knowledge and greater understanding. The third principle identified the university as a site for free enquiry and debate, distinguished by its openness to dialogue and rejection of intolerance. [...] The principles laid out in the Magna Charta Universitatum are as valid today as they were in 1988, and they are the necessary precondition for human advancement through enquiry, analysis and sound action.”⁵

The EUTOPIA TRAIN project needs to find out whether the participating institutions address these principles and ideals in their research and innovation strategies, and to what extent the concepts of academic freedom, addressing societal needs (as an inherent virtue), holistic education and research, truth-seeking free from government control and economic interests are shared fundamental values. In the following section, some of the common themes or perspectives will be accounted for.

⁴ European Universities Initiative Website: <https://education.ec.europa.eu/education-levels/higher-education/european-universities>

⁵ Magna Charta 2020: MCU 2020 — Observatory Magna Charta Universitatum, available at <http://www.magna-charta.org/magna-charta-universitatum/mcu-2020>.

1.1. Visions, strategies and policies

The EUTOPIA TRAIN universities have various names for the strategies: visions, strategies, or policies. They are, essentially, the same type of document with similar structures and content. And as any good strategy, they usually begin with bold opening statements.⁶

University of Warwick: *“Our commitment to research at Warwick is that it will be internationally leading, impactful, and provocative. It will change the world, making lives healthier, safer, more resilient, more just and more fulfilled. Our research produces transformative and lasting solutions to the multidisciplinary global challenges of both today and the future. Our research will maintain its foundation in disciplinary and interdisciplinary strengths. It will define the frontiers of knowledge and will take place in innovative multidisciplinary spaces.”*

The University of Gothenburg: *“University of Gothenburg's vision: **A university for the world**, confirms the university's ambition to be an international university that takes responsibility for the development of society and contributes to a sustainable world. [...] The vision clarifies the university's independent and societal foundation, not least with regard to the development of a sustainable world where education and research conducted at the university play a crucial role.*

Pompeu Fabra University: *“To train, by means of a rigorous, innovative and personalized educational model, people with a solid scientific and cultural background, general skills that can be adapted to the changes and challenges of society, and the specific skills they need to successfully carry out their life projects.”*

The Vrije Universiteit Brussels:

Mission statement: *The Vrije Universiteit Brussel is a university that aims to make an active contribution to a better society through research freedom, critical thinking, and an international orientation. In terms of research, the VUB aims to deliver high quality research that is both locally grounded and has strong international recognition.*

⁶ **University of Warwick:** *Our Research Strategy*, available at <https://warwick.ac.uk/research>, related to *Excellence with Purpose – University Strategy*, available at <https://warwick.ac.uk/about/strategy>.

University of Gothenburg: Vision 2021 – 2030: A University for the World, (<https://www.gu.se/en/about-the-university/vision-and-values/vision-2021-2030-a-university-for-the-world>), and *Universitetsgemensamma mål och strategier 2021 – 2024 (University-wide goals and strategies 2021-2024 Swedish only)* available at <https://medarbetarportalen.gu.se/organisation/vision-2021-2030/mal-strategier-aktiviteter/?languageId=100001&skipSSOCheck=true>.

Universitat Pompeu Fabra: The UPF Strategic Plan - Strategic Plan Pompeu Fabra University 2016 - 2025 (UPF), available at <https://www.upf.edu/en/web/plaestrategic/> and specifically <https://www.upf.edu/en/web/plaestrategic/mission-vision-values>.

Vrije Universiteit Brussel: Research and Innovation Strategy 2021 – 2024, (BELEIDSPLAN 2018-2022) available at <https://www.vub.be/en/research#vision,-policy-&-support>.

University of Ljubljana: *University of Ljubljana Strategy 2021 – 2020*, available at <https://warwick.ac.uk/about/strategy>.

CY Cergy Paris University: The Research policy - CY Cergy Paris Université, available at <https://www.cyu.fr/research-policy>.

University of Ljubljana Mission: *The University of Ljubljana implements and promotes basic, applied and developmental research and is pursuing excellence and the highest quality as well as the highest ethical criteria in all scientific fields and art. In these areas of national identity the University of Ljubljana specifically develops and promotes Slovenian scientific and professional terminology.*

Based on its own, Slovenian, and foreign research, the University of Ljubljana (UL) educates critical thinking top scientists, artists and professionals qualified for leading sustainable development, taking into account the tradition of the European Enlightenment and Humanism and with regard to human rights. Special attention is dedicated to developing talents.

CY Cergy Paris Université *Research at CY Cergy Paris Université is truly rooted in its territory, oriented towards the international market and business, and committed to addressing the challenges of tomorrow's world*

(---)

CY Cergy Paris Université is renowned for its dynamism and its firm commitment to developing research excellence. It is rooted in its territory and strongly oriented towards the international market. Its goal is to help address the challenges of the 21st century and it is committed to driving societal transition. (---) Its strong points are a better understanding of the global challenges of a changing world, due primarily to scientific and technological developments, coupled with a radically international approach, at the heart of a top-ranking campus for quality of life. CY Initiative systematically bases its implementation on two drivers: excellence in research and economic development.

The introductory statements all touch upon the same topics, show similar ambitions, and bear the same elements of the Humboldtian principles and the Magna Charta Universitatum. Their language may differ and some use phrases that are more strongly worded than others, but the core substance remains the same.

Each TRAIN institution is ambitious to uphold the ideals and virtues of academic freedom, truth seeking, holistic research and aspiration to make a positive impact and contribute to society through a transformation of the self, at the level of the alliance, and the world.

This report illustrates our findings with examples from the different research and innovation strategies. It will not, however, give examples from each EUTOPIA TRAIN University on each aspect of their R&I strategies, as it would be superfluous.

1.2. Examples of Impact & Innovation

With the ever-growing urgency of the threat of climate change and the increasing complexity of the challenges that comes in its wake, the need for Higher Education Institutions to contribute and tackle these challenges increases daily. This is emphasized from virtually all corners of society, from the European Union, member state governments, financiers, citizens, and industry.

The need of a system-level transformation has impacted strategies on all levels. Universities are often seen as structurally conservative but highly innovative in their output. This is why the European commission and governments are eager to play a part in the development of European universities. A part of this development is a stronger focus on innovation skills and capacity. Innovation and utilization stretch beyond immediate financial returns.

Universitat Pompeu Fabra (UPF) describes this in one of their stated missions: *To promote innovation and social transformation. We must transcend the institution's walls to generate synergies with society in order to contribute to social welfare and create value.*

UPF has the ambition to incorporate this within their research strategy and aspires to define a **cross-disciplinary research and innovation model throughout UPF**. They outline these six steps:

That has a fully international orientation in all areas of the university's research, [...]

That is able to establish relationships between teaching, research and transfer, [...]

That ensures that research and innovation results are visible to society everywhere, [...]

That is based on external processes for assessing research and knowledge transfer, [...]

That becomes a facilitating element for the doctoral and postdoctoral programmes, [...]

That is guided by the principles of responsible research and innovation (RRI), [...]

The university of Warwick has a similar approach:

Our refreshed Research Strategy will take a synergistic approach to impact and innovation, providing a framework in which impactful research is recognised, supported, and celebrated. Warwick faculty will be supported to deliver impact via the Warwick Impact Fund and through our portfolio of Impact Acceleration Accounts, with academically-led internal panels reviewing and awarding internal grants for innovative ideas with high potential for future impact.

Internal investment will be available to support a range of innovation activities, from industry-University secondments, industrial fellowships in areas of relevance to the Government's Industrial Strategy, collaborative research projects with practitioners in the public and private sector and with creative industries, 'industry engagement days', and 'proof of concept' and commercialisation funding. [...]

[...] Impact, outreach and public engagement are now included within academic promotion criteria and we will build on this by celebrating innovative and impactful research through impact events. [...]

The research and innovation strategy from The University of Ljubljana spans from 2012 and in part is a direct response to the 2009 financial crisis. It reflects how deep a financial crisis can affect the strategic decisions of a university and explicitly address urgent societal needs. The University of Ljubljana did not, in this setting, perceive itself as an isolated island but an actor within society that can, and should, contribute with direct and positive impacts to help with the recovery of the Slovenian economy. The strategic decision to focus on aiding the economic recovery can be seen as a confirmation that a university by its own accord can shift its priorities and respond to urgent societal needs without direct government or industry control and stay true to the previously mentioned academic ideals.

Their R&I strategy states: *[...] (the) Successful exit from the current crisis [2009 financial crisis] is dependent on inclusion of new technologies in the Slovenian economy, on use of new knowledge in the production processes.*

[...] This is the so-called third dimension of a university, which will be strengthened by the University of Ljubljana; the number and the value of the projects for economy, the public sector will be increased by a third in the 2020, and the number of participants in the lifelong programmes will be doubled. The measures are:

3.3.1. Formation of strategic and development partnerships, common development groups, implementation of development projects with economic organizations and the public sector.

3.3.2. Strengthening the office for technology transfer; formation promoting role of knowledge managers in transfer of basic knowledge for practical use as well as transfer of developmental challenges from the production environment into the research and development groups.

These three universities present holistic strategies to ensure synergies between disciplines, education, industry, and society at large to foster innovation and positive societal impact. They differ in tone, language, and sense of urgency but the core is the same. Innovation and utilization is an important aspect that is raised and emphasized within the research and innovations strategies of the EUTOPIA TRAIN partner universities.

Sustainable Development & Inclusion

The R&I The EUTOPIA TRAIN partner universities give a clear indication that each of them has incorporated sustainability as a part of their mission as academic institutions.

The University of Gothenburg:

During the period 2021–2024, the University of Gothenburg will:

- *clarify the University's role in the work for sustainable development,*
- *strengthen the development of sustainability perspectives in education and research,*
- *initiate and improve collaboration with organizations and other actors in the outside world,*
- *to contribute to sustainable societal development,*
- *reduce one's own negative environmental impact by continuing to develop a long-term one*
- *systematic sustainability work.*

The University of Warwick:

SUSTAINABILITY AND DEVELOPMENT

- *As sustainable development becomes increasingly important in the coming decades, this theme will be given greater prominence in Warwick's research*
- *This theme is aligned with the UN's Sustainable Development Goals, but still challenging of them We will tackle global challenges through truly interdisciplinary research across the arts and humanities, social sciences, science and medicine*
- *Our research will take place in multiple sectors, such as energy, agriculture, economy, finance, transport, urban science, environment, policy, education, materials, manufacturing and technology*
- *Examples include Energy politics and the transition to a zero-carbon world, culture and climate change and ethics in the Anthropocene.*

The topic of sustainability is present across the board. Each university mentions the importance of sustainable development as a key aspect and has it as a specific mission within their research and innovation strategies. They echo a key phrase within the Magna Charta Universitatum: “[...] precondition for human advancement through enquiry, analysis and sound action.”

The topic of sustainable development as a part of the research and innovation strategies for a university can easily be seen as a part of the continuous process of human advancement, incorporated as an aspect within research and education. Scientific enquiry, analysis, and sound action inherently is foundational building blocks of sustainable development. To specify the topic of sustainable development in a research and innovation strategy is, perhaps, a clarification for what the goal for these building blocks are.

1.3. The fundamentals of research

Research is at the core of every university. Without research, no new knowledge is produced that in turn can be disseminated through education or knowledge transfer to society to create impact.

The VUB Research Policy Plan 2018 – 2022 encompasses the essence of all the EUTOPIA TRAIN partner universities fundamentals for their respective research strategies:

The Vrije Universiteit Brussel is a free inquisitive, critical-thinking and internationally oriented university that wants to make an active and committed contribution to a better society. On research field, the VUB wants to deliver high-quality research with a strong local anchoring and a large international recognition.

VISION and STRATEGY:

In the coming years, the Vrije Universiteit Brussel wants to work on developing an optimal and future-proof research environment within a broader research data and open science policy, with attention to spearhead operation, core facilities and research management support. The objectives of the research policy focus on guaranteeing a healthy research culture and an appreciative personnel policy.

The principles of the research personnel policy are:

- 1. Permanent focus on maintaining a healthy research culture through the further development of a policy on scientific ethics and integrity,*
- 2. An appreciative personnel policy with a focus on administrative simplification, attention for training, career guidance and welfare and equality policy and attention to resources for researchers,*

The principles of the research policy in the field of research management and funding are:

- 1. A 'bottom-up' approach, where research is as much as possible from the research community is initiated and after selection on a quality basis,*
- 2. No a priori encryption of request-based resources, so that the best requests over all domains can be selected in competition on a discipline's own quality basis,*

3. *A healthy balance in internal financing between (I.) a general basic financing that all researchers provides access to research funding, (II.) promotion opportunities, and (III.) funding on excellence level,*

4. *Building in incentives for acquiring external financing, internationalization, networking and social valorisation in the criteria and conditions for internal financing instruments.*

There are a few recurring aspects within all of the EUTOPIA TRAIN partner universities research strategies that all revolve around two fundamental principles:

- Freedom of inquiry.
- A bottom-up approach to research.

Other aspects serve as supporting scaffolding to achieve these two fundamentals, for e.g.:

- Ideal working conditions for researchers
- Increased external funding
- Internationalization
- Societal impact
- Ethical research
- Excellent research
- Open science

The concept of a bottom-up approach recurs within all the EUTOPIA TRAIN strategies to the extent that one can argue that it is seen as a fundamental component for a university. The VUB research policy statement “[...] *developing an optimal and future-proof research environment [...]*” embodies this idea of an ideal/optimal environment that enables researchers to engulf themselves in free enquiry and scientific discovery. This report also dares to make a bold claim, that this is true for every university within the European union. A bottom-up approach is a consequence of the Humboldtian Ideals and principles of The Magna Charta Universitatum.

Conclusion on existing Research & Innovation strategies

Close analysis of the current R&I strategies of each individual Partner show that:

- The EUTOPIA TRAIN partner universities reflect the fundamentals of the Humboldtian Ideals and the Magna Charta Universitatum within their respective research and innovation strategies.
- The EUTOPIA TRAIN partner universities all state that sustainable development is an important/crucial virtue for a contemporary university.
- The EUTOPIA TRAIN partner universities all underline the importance of bottom-up approaches for creating the best environments for free inquiry and scientific discovery.
- The EUTOPIA TRAIN partner universities show similar ambitions of transferring new knowledge into society to create positive impacts, be it innovations or positive social impact by contributing to policy development.
- The EUTOPIA TRAIN partner universities all lay out similar types of missions/goals/themes within their respective research and innovation strategies.

Differences are mostly related to the wording, framing and respective weights of these shared building blocks within the visions, overarching themes and policies of each university.

Outcomes from EUTOPIA R&I SWOT (from Eutopia 2050)

In EUTOPIA 2050 a SWOT analysis has been conducted within wp 3.1.1. (project nr 612361). The SWOT is intended to identify the collective capabilities and interests to facilitate the identification of European and/or Global challenges aligning with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). In the following section we share the findings that are relevant to TRAIN and specifically this report.

1.4. Citations

Figure 1 shows total publications and publications related to SDGs. We do not have data from the other European alliances and therefore it is difficult to gauge the competitiveness of EUTOPIA in relation to other alliances. But the ratio of publications relating to SDGs is nevertheless rising.

Figure 1

Although each university has their own relative strengths and weaknesses, research related to almost all SDGs is broadly integrated at the EUTOPIA universities, and the current research output trend, as measured by number of publications, is positive.

1.5. Funding data

The analysis of funding data from Horizon 2020 up until January 2021 shows that:

- At least one EUTOPIA university participation in one out of every 40 projects. (0,63% of all EU contribution in €)
- We are relatively better in Excellent Science (ERC/MSCA), but large variation within EUTOPIA: room for sharing best practices within EUTOPIA.
- We are relatively weaker in the other programs, but large variation within EUTOPIA: we should use the variation for sharing best practices within EUTOPIA.

Summary Horizon 2020 funding data 2014 - 2020

- Total 782 signed grants (2,5% of H2020)
- 368M€ in EU contribution (0,63% of H2020)
 - Excellent Science: 232,3M€ (1,1% of total Excellent Science)
 - Industrial Leadership 33,5M€ (0,27% of total Industrial Leadership)
 - Societal Challenges 89,6M€ (0,41% of total Societal Challenges)
 - Other programs 12,6M€ (0,44% of total Other programs)

When compared to other European alliances the findings show that EUTOPIA ranks 16 of 41 of the alliances and that EUTOPIA has a similar funding profile compared to other alliances.

Horizon 2020 – Total EU contribution (M€)

The EUTOPIA alliance offers a complete platform for conducting research related to the SDGs and global challenges. EUTOPIA is therefore well-positioned to use the SDGs as a focus area, and has potential to become a well-recognized hub for challenge-driven research relating to the SDGs.

Although the SWOT shows that there are great potentials for future collaborations regarding the SDGs and global challenges, we still need to decide how to balance a top-down and a bottom-up approach, while at the same time assuring a responsible and sustainable research and innovation community. We want to make sure that we continue to advance blue-sky research and foster a competitive and innovative researcher community in the future.

Should we define overarching EUTOPIA themes in the common R&I agenda?

A joint EUTOPIA R&I strategy should provide added value to each of the institutional members of EUTOPIA and promote excellence in research and innovation to a level that cannot be reached by a single institution. All institutions want to promote excellence – the question is how to do it in a way that is relevant to EUTOPIA.

It is a complicated task for any university to develop a new research and innovation strategy, weighing in both the external and internal political considerations and the core of academic freedom. It is a time-consuming process involving many individual researchers, evaluation boards and discussion fora. With this in mind and the fact that EUTOPIA universities' current research and innovation strategies mirror each other, it is reasonable to utilize these in the forthcoming development of a common EUTOPIA Research and Innovation agenda.

During discussions between the members of EUTOPIA TRAIN institutions, the conclusion so far is that we want to focus on providing our institutions with structures, culture and support that enhances creativity, quality, and openness. With a shared bottom-up approach, it is not in our mutual interest to define what challenges our researchers tackle – it is in our interest to facilitate and support the structures, individuals and connected EUTOPIA communities. One way of moving forward in this direction could be to base the agenda on a few common principles rather than defining specific research themes. This is what the vice presidents of research and innovation within the alliance will be discussing during the next months.

A pilot call is to be launched within EUTOPIA 2050 on Connecting research communities. The outcome of the call could (if successful) be a part of implementing a bottom-up approach in the common agenda. Current efforts within in the EUTOPIA 2050, SIF and TRAIN projects have the potential to increase the formation of EUTOPIA researcher networks, ultimately increasing EUTOPIA total research output.

